

Ecosphere

Influence of biomimicry structures on ecosystem function in a Rocky Mountain incised stream

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Appendix S1

Table S1. Top five producing taxa by treatment by production (P; mg AFDM m⁻² d⁻¹), standing biomass (B; mg AFDM m⁻²), and density (N; ind m⁻²). Shown are medians for taxa with 95% confidence intervals.

Beaver	P	B	N
(Richness = 35)	(mg AFDM m ⁻² d ⁻¹)	(mg AFDM m ⁻²)	(ind m ⁻²)
<i>Baetis sp.</i>	5.08 (2.24 -16.18)	245.19 (92.84 - 743.08)	1091.94 (864.70 – 4,362.97)
<i>Tipula sp.</i>	4.79 (0 – 10.79)	424.28 (0 - 922.08)	7.18 (0 - 21.53)
<i>Hygrotus sp.</i>	3.69 (3.69 – 6.17)	271.86 (271.86 - 461.58)	57.41 (57.41 - 86.11)
Chironomidae			
Non-Tanypodinae	3.20 (2.00 – 5.19)	111.44 (70.25 - 178.06)	7,777.53 (4,329.31 – 19,078.44)
<i>Heterlimnius</i>	2.51 (1.24 – 3.80)	120.33 (60.76 - 191.13)	391.09 (248.77 - 588.43)
Mimic			
(Richness = 40)			
<i>Pteronarcella sp.</i>	3.56 (0 – 13.28)	279.75 (0 – 1,108.62)	17.94 (0 - 57.41)
<i>Helicopsyche sp.</i>	3.41	172.28	394.08

	(1.16 – 7.68)	(65.64 - 385.30)	(182.99 - 864.70)
<i>Tipula sp.</i>	2.85	242.45	26.91
	(1.01 – 5.9)	(72.04 - 528.03)	(17.94 - 43.06)
<i>Ceratopsyche sp.</i>	2.55	148.43	157.87
	(0.70 – 4.52)	(39.70 - 259.53)	(32.29 - 287.04)
Chironomidae.			
Tanypodinae	2.05	91.14	593.81
	(0.18 – 5.14)	(6.91 - 230.71)	(136.31 - 1269.04)

Reference

(Richness = 42)

<i>Tipula sp.</i>	2.21	186.40	10.76
	(0.66 – 2.21)	(41.07 - 186.40)	(10.76 - 10.76)
<i>Hydrobiidae sp.</i>	1.84	106.05	144.71
	(0.60 – 3.82)	(31.10 - 224.20)	(65.18 - 243.38)
<i>Arctopsyche sp.</i>	1.11	92.32	7.18
	(0.68 – 1.11)	(55.36 - 92.32)	(5.38 - 7.18)
<i>Lymnaeidae sp.</i>	0.95	77.75	26.91
	(0.01 – 2.88)	(0.61 - 196.14)	(5.38 - 165.65)
<i>Limnephilus sp.</i>	0.92	70.74	3.59
	(0.92 - 0.92)	(70.74 - 70.74)	(3.59 - 3.59)

Figure S1. Non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) ordination of macroinvertebrate densities and vectors of basal resources and physical variables in Beaver (black crosses and fill), Mimic (orange inverted triangles and fill), and Reference (blue squares and fill) treatments. Each point is a sampling date and convex hulls delineate the bounds of each treatment among all samples. Community structure showed substantial overlap among treatments, however, subtle differences among treatments were detectable. NMDS-1 was positively loaded for D_{50} , discharge (“Q_cfs), suspended FPOM and suspended CPOM, and negatively loaded for CPOM, fine sediment, biofilm, and suspended FPOM, . NMDS-2 was positively loaded for CPOM, D_{50}

and suspended CPOM, and negatively loaded for fine sediment, biofilm, discharge, and suspended FPOM.